

NUANCES OF CONSTRUCTIVIST TEACHER'S MANTLE

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Abstract

This paper brings into discussion about the role of teachers in diverse atmosphere based on various constructivist perspectives. Respectively, this paper puts emphasis on the voyage of constructivism in Indian Education. This study further takes a closer look on nuances of constructivist teachers' mantle. This research article mainly focused on teachers' mantle in various types of constructivism namely, personal constructivist perspective, cognitive constructivist perspective, social constructivist perspective and radical constructivist perspective. Finally, this paper tinted the teachers' mantle in principles behind teaching approaches based on constructivism. So the nuances of a teacher's mantle as a constructivist teacher depend on the teachers' individual interest. This paper will stimulate the teachers' curiosity towards constructivism pedagogical approaches.

Keywords: Constructivism, radical constructivist, social constructivist, cognitive constructivist

CONSTRUCTIVISM

Constructivism is actually a philosophy and theory and not pedagogy. Constructivist philosophy is a description of knowledge rather than a prescription for learning. Foote, Vermette and Battaglia (2001) also view Constructivism as a descriptive entity: "Constructivism describes the processes undergone by the learner during instruction". Constructivism, then, is a philosophy that views knowledge as a subjective process that is shaped and structured by one's experiences. As a person encounters new experiences and situations, he connects these new experiences to previous knowledge bases and understandings. These connections not only add to the original knowledge base but also restructure that pre-existing knowledge base [5].

VOYAGE OF CONSTRUCTIVISM PEDAGOGY IN INDIAN EDUCATION

Pedagogy is the discourse with which one needs to engage in order both to teach intelligently and make sense of teaching – for discourse and act are independent, and there can be no teaching without pedagogy or pedagogy without teaching [8]. There are many pedagogical practices based on constructivism principles. Activity based learning and Active Learning Methods are based on constructivism principles [1]. Tamil Nadu has pioneered many educational initiatives such as Joyful learning , ABL and ALM which have attracted fair amount of appreciation in the media, in other States and some countries [13]. ABL methodology is based on the pedagogic principle of learning through activities. It is an approach which took root in Tamil Nadu (India) and its defining characteristic is its promotion of student learning as self-initiated, independent and at an individual pace [16]. Bonwell and Eison state active learning method as "...that students must do more than just listen: They must read, write, discuss, or be engaged in solving problems. Most important, to be actively involved, students must engage in such higher-order thinking tasks as analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. Within this context, it is proposed that strategies promoting active learning be defined as instructional activities

involving students in doing things and thinking about what they are doing." There is a consensus among researchers that we do not learn by passively receiving, and then remembering what we are taught. Learning involves actively constructing our own meanings. Actually construction of connections between neurons happens as we invent our own concepts and ideas, connected to what we already know. This "meaning-making" theory of learning is called 'constructivism'. We must remember that neuronal connections are happening all the time. The question is whether we are aware of the connections being made. Thus active learning seems to involve an inward looking, simultaneous with the outward looking. Active learning refers to techniques where students do more than simply listen to a lecture. Students are DOING something including discovering, processing, and applying information [4]. The NCF (2009) requires a teacher to be a facilitator of children's learning in a manner that helps children to construct knowledge and meaning. The teacher in this process is a co-creator of knowledge. Teachers need to view learners as active participants in their own learning and not as mere recipients of knowledge; need to encourage their capacity to construct knowledge; ensure that learning shifts away from rote methods. Teachers need to be trained in organizing learner-centred, activitybased, participatory learning experiences – play, projects, discussion, dialogue, observation, visits, integrating academic learning with productive work [14]. Draft National Education Policy (2019) pointed out that NCERT textbooks will be revised to first contain only the essential core material in each subject, keeping in mind a constructivist, discovery-based, analysis-based, engaging, and enjoyable style of learning in accordance with the revised NCF. And also Draft NEP (2019) highlighted that the reduction in, and increased flexibility of, school curriculum content - and the renewed emphasis on constructivist rather than rote learning - must be accompanied by parallel changes in school textbooks. All textbooks shall aim to contain the essential core material (together with discussion, analysis, examples, and applications) deemed important on a national level, but at the same time contain any desired nuances and supplementary material in accordance with local contexts and needs [12].

NUANCES OF CONSTRUCTIVIST TEACHER'S MANTLE

- Teaching for constructivist learning implies various roles for the teacher and the student that are markedly different to those in traditional transmission classrooms[17]. A Constructivist teacher views his role as one of managing the learning environment and acting as guide, facilitator and coach; the role of the Constructivist teacher is not one of transmitting knowledge. A Constructivist teacher thinks less about content and more about how to manage a class environment in which the learner interacts with materials and the world around him [15]. The learning environment should be designed to support and challenge the learners thinking. The learner should own the problem and the process of finding solutions, so that he becomes a truly creative thinker. This is possible if the teacher becomes consultant and coach [1]. One cannot think of constructivist teaching, however, as a monolithic, agreed-upon concept. The extent of the agreement among the various constructivist approaches is that constructivism is a meaning-making theory. It suggests that individuals create their own new understandings based upon the interaction of what they already know and believe, and the phenomena or ideas with which they come into contact [9].
- Learning is not the result of development; learning is development. It requires invention and self-organization on the part of the learner. Thus, teachers need to allow learners to raise their own questions generate their own hypotheses and models as possibilities, test them out for viability, and defend and discuss them in communities of discourse and practice [3].
- Errors need to be perceived as a result of learners' conceptions, and therefore not minimized or avoided. Challenging, open ended investigations in realistic, meaningful contexts need to be offered by teachers which allow learners to explore and generate many possibilities, both affirming and contradictions, in particular, need to be illuminated, explored and discussed [3].

- Dialogue within a community engenders further thinking. The classroom needs to be seen as a “community of discourse engaged in activity, reflection and conversation”. The learners (rather than teacher) are responsible for defending, proving, justifying and communicating their ideas to the classroom community. Ideas are accepted as truth only insofar as they make sense to the community and thus they rise to the level of “taken-as-shared” [3].
- Teacher as Guide: The teacher becomes a guide for the learner, providing bridging or scaffolding, helping to extend the learners’ zone of proximal development. The student is encouraged to develop metacognitive skills such as reflective thinking and problem solving techniques. The independent learner is intrinsically motivated to generate, discover, build and enlarge her/his own framework of knowledge [18].
- Teachers as Facilitators: Constructivism wants teachers to facilitate the process of learning of the students. It also wants teachers to give up their desire to lecture on the contents of textbooks or other materials. A facilitator helps the learner to understand the content by creatively using his mind. The emphasis shifts from the instructor and the content towards the learner. In this role the teacher needs to have very different skills than while delivering lectures. A teacher tells, a facilitator inspires; a teacher lectures, a facilitator supports; a teacher gives answers, a facilitator creates the environment for the learner to arrive at his own conclusions; a teacher gives monologue, a facilitator has a dialogue with the learners [1].
- Dynamic interaction between task, instructor and learner: As per constructivism, the instructor and the learners are equally involved in learning from each other. The learning experience is both subjective and objective. The culture, values and background of the instructor become very important in interplay between learners and their tasks in the shaping of meaning. Learners link their truth with that of the instructor and the fellow learners. This gives a new socially trusted version of truth. This creates a dynamic interaction between the task, the instructor and the learner. The learners and instructors have to become aware of each others’ view points and then look at their own beliefs, standards and values. This makes learning both subjective and objective at the same time [1].

TEACHERS’ MANTLE IN VARIOUS TYPES OF CONSTRUCTIVISM

- ***In Personal constructivist perspective:*** From a personal constructivist perspective, teachers would focus on the knowledge of the individual learner and would see learning as an active and continuous process. They would take the view that learners have the final responsibility for their own learning and that teaching is the ‘promotion of opportunities and support for learning’ [17].
- ***In cognitive constructivist perspective:*** According to cognitive constructivists, development leads to learning. Piaget proposed that stage-wise development of mental schemes leads to learning. When children encounter new problems, they engage in a process of assimilation and accommodation, relying on and making modifications of existing experience to achieve new understanding. One way for teachers to promote assimilation is to facilitate age-appropriate games. However, in response to challenges by neo-Piagetians that stages are fluid rather than static, teachers can also extend childrens’ learning beyond their current levels of development [21].
- ***In Social constructivist perspective:*** A Social constructivist perspective would place more emphasis on how classroom environments support learning. It would focus ‘attention on the social process operating in the classroom in which a teacher promotes a discourse community in which students and teachers ‘co-construct’ knowledge’ [17].
- ***In Radical Constructivist perspective:*** Radical constructivism is a theory of knowing which, for reasons that had nothing to do with teaching mathematics or education, does not accept this commonsense perspective. Instead, it takes seriously the no less venerable suggestion that what a teacher sees when he or she looks at a student is necessarily part of the particular teachers’

experience and, as such, the result of the particular teachers' way and means of perceiving and conceptualizing what is being perceived. Thus, the teachers' view of the student, the classroom and its furniture, the surroundings of the school house, the classmates, the students family, the school books and other educational material. the curriculum, and needless to say, the teachers' views about education, are and cannot be anything but the particular teachers' own experiential world. From an educators' point of view, one of the most important features of radical constructivism is the sharp distinction it draws between teaching and training. The first aims at generating understanding, and the second at competent performance [5].

TEACHERS' MANTLE IN PRINCIPLES OF CONSTRUCTIVISM APPROACHES

The constructivist view of learning has generated a number of teaching approaches based on the following four key principles or values:

In Active Learning: The teacher must understand the students' pre-existing conceptions and guide the activity to address, build on and refine pre-existing conceptions [6].

In Scaffolded Learning: In the classroom, a scaffold is a set of activities designed by the teacher to assist the learner in moving through increasingly difficult tasks to master a new skill. The teacher designs the classroom activities based on the students' prior knowledge; that is, for example, what they learned previously in the classroom or perhaps through other life experiences. Classroom activities are designed to help move students from point A to point B, to progress from what they know to what they need to know to complete the course or the class unit – to bring them through the zone of proximal development to achieve their potential [6].

In Collaborative Learning: The teacher becomes a facilitator of learning, organizing, monitoring, supporting and intervening where appropriate. The teacher is not in the role of imparter of knowledge, firing questions at pupils – 'chalk and talk' of common classroom practice [7]. And also the teacher provides information to build background knowledge needed for the student to fully understand the content. The teacher needs to deepen student background knowledge in specific areas [2].

In Learning by doing: Teachers become more confident in their role as developers and facilitators of the learning activities. Teachers also admit that in organizing these activities, they see themselves more as facilitators, and that they had to share their responsibilities with their students, leaving behind the idea that they are the only people responsible for reaching the learning objectives [19].

CONCLUSION

Effective teaching requires that the teacher gives pupils plenty of opportunities to contribute and elaborate their own ideas, and that he or she genuinely listens to what pupils say (or are trying to say), and attempts to consider this from the pupils' perspective. To some extent this means that the teacher needs to accept the value of each pupils' contribution and the relevance of the pupils' experience [10]. Effective teachers have an optimistic attitude about being a teacher and about their students [20]. As might be imagined, conceiving of teaching in a constructivist mode implies a number of conceptual shifts and, indeed, breaks, which inevitably create repercussions for teaching practices as well as for teacher education and "professional development" [11]. There is an urgent need to update teacher education programmes, to staff the teaching profession with highly skilled on Constructivism. The teachers should be considered their classroom as laboratories where experiments can be conducted to create their teaching more consequential to the students. Teacher as a real pedagogue always look for new pedagogical strategies. The nuances of a teacher's mantle as a constructivist teacher depend on the teachers' individual interest. This paper will stimulate the teachers' curiosity towards constructivism pedagogical approaches.

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